

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 116

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 116

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 116:1 "I love the LORD, because He ^bhears My voice <i>and</i> my supplications. ² Because He has "inclined His ear to me, Therefore I shall call <i>upon Him</i> as long as I live. ³ The "cords of death encompassed me And the ¹terrors of ²Sheol ³came upon me; I found distress and sorrow. ⁴ Then "I called upon the name of the LORD: "O LORD, I beseech You, ^{1b}save my life!"</p>	<p>Psa. 116:1 אֶת־קוֹלִי תִחַנּוּנָי׃ ² כִּי־הִטָּה אָזְנוֹ לִי וּבִימִי אָקְרָא׃ ³ אֶפְפוּנִי חֲבִלֵי־מָוֶת וּמִצָּרֵי שְׂאוֹל מִצְאוּנֵי צָרָה וַיִּגְוֶן אֶמְצָא׃ ⁴ וּבְשֵׁם־יְהוָה אָקְרָא אֲנִי׃ יְהוָה מִלְּטָה נַפְשִׁי׃ ⁵ תַּחֲנוּן יְהוָה וְצַדִּיק וְאֱלֹהֵינוּ מֵרַחֵם׃ ⁶ שֹׁמֵר פְּתָאִים יְהוָה דַּלּוֹתַי וְלִי יְהוֹשִׁיעַ׃ ⁷ שׁוּבִי נַפְשִׁי לְמִנוּחַיִכִי כִי־יְהוָה גָּמַל עָלַיִכִי׃ ⁸ כִּי חִלַּצְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִלְּמָוֶת אֶת־עֵינַי מִן־דְּמָעָה אֶת־רַגְלִי מִדָּחַי׃ ⁹ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ לִפְנֵי יְהוָה בְּאַרְצוֹת הַחַיִּים׃ ¹⁰ הֵאֱמַנְתִּי כִי אֲדַבֵּר אֲנִי עָנִיתִי מְאֹד׃ ¹¹ אֲנִי אֲמַרְתִּי בְּחַפְזִי כָּל־הָאָדָם כֹּזֵב׃ ¹² מָה־אָשִׁיב לַיהוָה כָּל־תַּגְּמוֹלוֹתַי עָלַי׃ ¹³ כּוֹס־יְשׁוּעוֹת אֵשָׂא וּבְשֵׁם יְהוָה אָקְרָא׃ ¹⁴ גִּדְרֵי לַיהוָה אֲשַׁלֵּם נִגְדָה־נָּא לְכָל־עַמּוֹ׃ ¹⁵ יָקָר בְּעֵינַי יְהוָה הַמְּוֹתָה לַחֲסִידָיו׃ ¹⁶ אֲנִי יְהוָה כִּי־אֲנִי עֲבַדְךָ אֲנִי־עַבְדְּךָ בֶן־אֲמָתֶךָ כְּפַתְחַת לְמוֹסְרֵי׃ ¹⁷ לָךְ־אֲזַבַּח זִבְחַת תּוֹדָה וּבְשֵׁם יְהוָה אָקְרָא׃ ¹⁸ גִּדְרֵי לַיהוָה אֲשַׁלֵּם</p>
<p>Psa. 116:5 "Gracious is the LORD, and ^brighteous; Yes, our God is "compassionate. ⁶ The LORD preserves "the simple; I was ^bbrought low, and He saved me. ⁷ Return to your "rest, O my soul, For the LORD has ^bdealt bountifully with you. ⁸ For You have "rescued my soul from death, My eyes from tears, My feet from stumbling. ⁹ I shall walk before the LORD In the ^{1a}land of the living. ¹⁰ I "believed when I said, "I am ^bgreatly afflicted." ¹¹ I "said in my alarm,</p>	

“^bAll men are liars.”

Psa. 116:12 What shall I ^arender
to the LORD

For all His ^bbenefits ¹toward me?

¹³ I shall lift up the ^acup of salvation
And ^bcall upon the name of the
LORD.

¹⁴ I shall ^apay my vows to the LORD,
Oh *may it be* ^bin the presence of all
His people.

¹⁵ ^aPrecious in the sight of the LORD
Is the death of His godly ones.

¹⁶ O LORD, ¹surely I am ^aYour
servant,

I am Your servant, the ^bson of
Your handmaid,

You have ¹loosed my bonds.

¹⁷ To You I shall offer ^aa sacrifice of
thanksgiving,

And ^bcall upon the name of the
LORD.

¹⁸ I shall ^apay my vows to the LORD,
Oh *may it be* in the presence of all

His people,

¹⁹ In the ^acourts of the LORD’S
house,

In the midst of you, O ^bJerusalem.

¹Praise ²the LORD!

נְגִידָה-נָא לְכָל-עַמּוֹ : ¹⁹ בְּתַצְרוֹת |
בֵּית יְהוָה בְּתוֹכֵי יְרוּשָׁלַם הַלְלוּ-
יְהוָה :

References

Psalm 116:1

^aPs 18:1

^bPs 6:8; 66:19; Is 37:17; Dan 9:18

Psalm 116:2

^aPs 17:6; 31:2; 40:1

Psalm 116:3

¹Lit *straits*

²I.e. the nether world

³Lit *found me*

^aPs 18:4, 5

Psalm 116:4

¹Or *deliver my soul*

^aPs 18:6; 118:5

^bPs 17:13; 22:20

Psalm 116:5

^aPs 86:15; 103:8

^bEzra 9:15; Neh 9:8; Ps 119:137; 145:17; Jer 12:1; Dan 9:14

^cEx 34:6

Psalm 116:6

^aPs 19:7; Prov 1:4

^bPs 79:8; 142:6

Psalm 116:7

^aJer 6:16; Matt 11:29

^bPs 13:6; 142:7

Psalm 116:8

^aPs 49:15; 56:13; 86:13

Psalm 116:9

¹Lit *lands*

^aPs 27:13

Psalm 116:10

^a2 Cor 4:13

^bPs 88:7

Psalm 116:11

^aPs 31:22

^bPs 62:9; Rom 3:4

Psalm 116:12

¹Lit *upon*

^a2 Chr 32:25; 1 Thess 3:9

^bPs 103:2

Psalm 116:13

^aPs 16:5

^bPs 80:18; 105:1

Psalm 116:14

^aPs 50:14; 116:18

^bPs 22:25

Psalm 116:15

^aPs 72:14

Psalm 116:16

¹Or *because*

^aPs 86:16; 119:125; 143:12

^bPs 86:16

^cPs 107:14

Psalm 116:17

^aLev 7:12; Ps 50:14

^bPs 116:13

Psalm 116:18

^aPs 116:14

Psalm 116:19

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 92:13; 96:8; 135:2
^bPs 102:21

Targum

Psa. 116:1 I love, for the LORD will hear my voice, my prayer. ² For he has inclined his ear to me, and I call [to him] throughout my days. ³ The sicknesses of death surrounded me, and the pains of Sheol found me; pain and sorrow I will find. ⁴ And in the name of the LORD I will call out: Please, O LORD, save my soul. ⁵ The LORD is gracious and righteous, and our God is merciful. ⁶ The LORD observes enticements; I became poor, and it was meet to redeem me. ⁷ Return, O my soul, to your place of rest, for the word of the LORD has repaid you with good. ⁸ For you have delivered my soul from being killed, my eyes from tears, my feet from stumbling. ⁹ I will walk before the LORD in the land of the living. ¹⁰ I have believed, therefore I will speak; in the assembly of the righteous I have sung much praise. ¹¹ I said when I fled, “All the sons of men are liars.” ¹² How will I repay in the presence of the LORD all his kind favors that are shown to me? ¹³ The cup of redemption I will carry in the age to come, and I will call on the name of the LORD. ¹⁴ I will repay my vows in the presence of the LORD, I will tell now his miracles to all his people. ¹⁵ Honorable in the presence of the LORD is the death that is sent to his pious ones. ¹⁶ Please, O LORD; for I am your servant; I am your servant, the son of your handmaiden, you have loosened my bonds. ¹⁷ To you I will sacrifice the sacrifice of slaughter, and call out in the name of the LORD. ¹⁸ I will repay my vows in the presence of the LORD, I will tell now his miracles to all his people. ¹⁹ In the courts of the sanctuary of our God, in your midst, O Jerusalem. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm of David starts with David saying that he loved the LORD because he knew that the LORD was hearing his voice. Despite the harassment that Saul was doing, David placed his love in the LORD's protection. When a messenger brought David the news that Saul was dead, he was greatly disturbed. The man boasted that he killed David's enemy. David ordered the man to be executed because Saul was the anointed of the LORD (2 Samuel 1:14).

The Talmud in Rosh Hashanah (16b-17a) explains that this Psalm is about the Final Judgment at the end of time. There is to be a Great Resurrection of the dead at that time. The average people will be saved from Sheol because the LORD will hear their cries and will forgive them.

Notes on the Psalm

Verse eighteen is an important verse to remember. One must fulfill vows made to the LORD. Numerous times people make agreements with the LORD in that they will do something for the LORD if the LORD does something for them. Most of the time, the person making the vow does not fulfill their part of the agreement. It is imperative that if a person takes a vow that the person completes it before judgment day. Since no one knows how long they will live, it is imperative to fulfill all committed vows.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

